

MICROMECHANICS - FOUNDATIONS AND CHALLENGES

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ABSTRACT

Micromechanics are necessary to understand the build up of stress from the end of a fibre in a deformed composite; to understand pull-out; to understand multiple cracking both in uniaxial composites and in laminates. Direct measurements for the elastic case are available and these will be compared with experiment. For the non elastic case various approximations are available and these are briefly reviewed.

Micromechanics have not so far provided a satisfactory theory of the interface between fibre and matrix. This is partly because of the fact that the diameter of useful fibres falls within a range, namely a few microns, in which a transition must occur between a regime in which cohesive forces governed by surface energy considerations (small sizes), to one in which normal engineering methods of joining by adhesion and the use of additional chemical agents or physical methods of keying, applies. The two approaches are sketched so as to see if a synthesis is possible.

Lastly, micro-packing considerations rather than micromechanical consideration will be used in order to see whether isotropic fibre composites could be useful.

1. INTRODUCTION

We will principally be concerned with fibre composites. Micromechanics is the science of understanding the possible arrangements of fibres and of matrix and how these affect the mechanical and other physical and chemical properties. Engineers like to avoid having to consider what they regard as the niceties of the design of a material and prefer to be given the values of the properties of the composite considered as a homogeneous material.

In many cases this is not a defensible stance if composites are to be used intelligently and their modes of behaviour in service understood. Analysis of the properties of all engineering materials throughout their life from fabrication to ultimate disposal is now becoming of central importance (1) so that modes of damage during service due to mechanical and chemical stresses must be understood, the environmental impact of the material considered and the means of eventual disposal. In the case of composites this last may mean separating fibres from matrix and other constituents (fillers, sizes, adhesives) and disposing of each separately. Modes of chemical attack, regarded as disadvantageous in some instances may appear as a benefit when ultimate disposal is in mind.

2. TRANSFER LENGTHS - CRITICAL LENGTHS - PULL-OUT LENGTHS, PUSH-OUT LENGTHS

2.1 Experiment

Understanding the build up of stress in a fibre near to its end is one of the original problems in the micromechanics of composites as well as one of the most enduring. It affects the modulus and strength of short fibre composites, stress concentration at the breaks, toughness via pull-out and debonding. When the matrix breaks rather than the fibre then again there are transfer lengths to consider which affect multiple cracking in laminates and in CMCs and all the hysteretic phenomena associated with multiple fracture. An analogous concept arises in the joining of composites. In all of these problems an understanding of the micromechanics is vital. Although the way in which stress builds up from a fibre end has been qualitatively understood for decades what is now needed is an experimental method able to produce reliable results for any system and a general theory which can be applied so as to predict or suggest results if any two (or more) materials are being considered for fibre and matrix combinations. It is not enough to study stresses in a single isolated fibre; the effect of other neighbouring fibres must be known and the mechanical properties of the matrix, close to a fibre.

Direct measurements of the stress build up from a fibre end have been attempted originally by photoelasticity e.g. Allison and Holloway (2). Laser Raman spectroscopy (LRS) is a very powerful technique of general applicability to dielectric fibres - well reviewed recently by Galiotis (3) and by Young et al (4). It is used in the semiconductor industry to investigate strain in silicon wafers. The atomic vibrational frequencies are measured which are related to the interatomic distances and hence a direct means of strain is possible, which is highly selective and capable of probing areas as small as four square microns. As usually used the technique requires calibration and so the relationship between Raman frequency and tensile strain is obtained by stressing a single fibre in air on a micrometer while Raman spectra are taken along the length at each level of applied load. The difference between the frequency under load and that of the free standing fibre represents the frequency shift which turns out to be linear with strain. The stress build up follows qualitatively the original suggestion based on the notion of non-elastic behaviour close to the fibre end - an example is shown in Fig.1 for a single kevlar 49 fibre in an epoxy matrix (Ciba-Geigy 927). The agreement in a qualitative fashion with classical ideas is clear - in particular the lack of stress-transfer across the end of the fibre.

Figure 1
 Axial tensile strain in the fibre as a function of distance from the end.
 C_m = level of matrix strain.
 System: Kevlar 49 - CG927 epoxy
 From: reference 3 with permission

Melanitis et al (5) studied the fragmentation test in the important carbon fibre/epoxy (C-G MY750) system. The average strain in the fibre increased (linearly) with applied strain to 0.8% when fibre fracture occurred. The fibre strain then built up from the tips as expected and it was established that the interfaced shear stress was affected, first increasing as successive fractures occurred to a maximum value of 42 MPa at 1.8% applied strain and decreased thereafter. Assuming an approximately constant fibre strength the estimated value of the interface shear strength (ISS) after complete fragmentation was about half the value measured by LRS. In the same powerful paper comparison is made between LRS derived values of ILS and those found by pull out and push out tests.

The use of these tests in particular is reviewed by Young et al (4) together with the microbend test. Although rather extravagant claims are made for wide divergence from current theory the qualitative picture of, initially elastic strain being superseded by yielding through debond at the interface is not greatly modified though it is made more quantitative. In addition, it is now becoming possible with these techniques to measure initial prestress in fibre and in the matrix (?) when this is due to either difference in thermal expansion coefficients or to stresses produced during curing.

Another very useful technique is fluorescence spectroscopy, Ma and Clarke (6), who use a technique developed by Grabnev (7) to detect stress in single crystals of sapphire containing chromium 3+. Provided the chromium iron is tightly bound there is a direct linear relationship between the shift of the fluorescence peak and the state of elastic strain. In this case there is no appreciable broadening accompanying the shift. Fluorescence spectroscopy, as used by Ma and Clarke, requires knowledge of which of the six possible stress components is actually being measured. Were sufficient different frequencies of fluorescences available this disadvantage could be turned to account to measure all six components at particular points within a composite. The method of using fluorescence from individual ions has not been developed as much as the Raman spectroscopy of the spectral lines of the fibre itself but is useful in ceramics particularly to investigate the push out test and could, of course, in principle be used at elevated temperatures as indeed may the LRS method.

These techniques are very important because they are capable of measuring the stress state in the composite before an external strain is imposed i.e. the residual stress.

2.2 Theory

Apart from the many variants of the shear lag method due to Cox (8) there are few reliable theoretical estimates of the stress in the fibre and matrix close to a fibre end. Most theories of short fibre composites are more concerned to find the overall elastic modull of an aligned composite e.g. Chou (9). Among these metal matrix composite specialists often use Eshelly's method e.g. (10). Eshelly's theory is quite exact for a single ellipsoidal inclusion and some approximation can be made for multiple inclusions. An important part of it is that it points up the importance of the mean stress within the matrix which arises when a fibrous composite is stressed. This mean stress is most important for understanding hysteresis on loading and unloading. However, Eshelly's theory entails a uniform stress within the inclusion; finding the stress variation in the fibre is the essence of the problem here.

More sophisticated theories than simple shear lag are due to Whitney and Drzal (11) and to Nairn (12) and McCartney (13) has a very exact solution for a fibre break. These theories do allow for debonding. There are also finite element calculations e.g. (14). The experimentalists seem shy of really engaging themselves with these theories.

The case of the cracked matrix and bridging fibre is, in a sense, a sort of dual of the case of the fibre end or more precisely, two closely abutting fibre ends. Theoretical treatments of multiple (and single) matrix cracking have been usefully collated by McCartney (15) who reviews shear lag models, a new multiple cylinder model, variational models and complete solution techniques both for fully elastic assumptions and with slippage at the

interface allowed. He believes that sufficient understanding of the micromechanics is now available for adequate prediction of the thermoelastic properties of cracked composites.

The fibre end problem has not yet been surveyed competently in the same way. McCartney believes that the modified shear lag model is adequate for fibre fragmentation tests and even for pull out tests. If perfect bonding can be assumed then the Nayfeh (16) and Nuismer and Tan (17) variation of shear lag are said to be adequate. However, the perfectly bonded assumption for fibre end problems is of little physical interest, in my opinion, since it only pertains at very small composite strains.

In summary, we now have experimental and theoretical methods which can be used to determine quantities such as the interfacial shear stress and transfer length to considerable accuracy but the experimental method must be chosen for the particular system and a unified theoretical treatment is needed. Experimental determination of the initial stress state within fibre and matrix in the unloaded composite, i.e. determination of the residual stresses is now to my mind the most important problem in this area, since without it, theories of crack suppression, of hysteresis, and hence understanding of fatigue, cannot be properly applied.

3. ADHESION BETWEEN FIBRE AND MATRIX

Understanding the mechanical interaction at the fibre/matrix interface is the central problem of the materials science of composites. A most important part of this is the physics and chemistry of adhesion. Yet so important an issue is hardly mentioned in a volume devoted to Interfaces in Composites (18). When considering "stiction" (Leslie Phillips' word for it) at an interface it is usual to start by considering the work of adhesion W (energy per unit area) which is the reversible work required to separate (pull apart?) a unit area of the interface. After separation each equal surface has free surface energy γ , half of W , which can pull the surfaces back into contact. For surfaces between dissimilar materials

$$W = \gamma_1 + \gamma_2 - \gamma_{12} \quad [1]$$

(Dupré equation)

Work of adhesion is useful because it distinguishes two states: contact (which is not precisely defined at this stage) and separation. The forces between molecules of the two surfaces act over very short distances - for van der Waals forces (i.e. those between saturated molecules) all but 1% the work is done when the surfaces are separated by 1 nm. For other types of bonding covalent, ionic smaller distance would be involved - the force may not actually be measurable because surfaces jump together; but cf the atomic force microscope (19). The fact that really clean and smooth surfaces between solids spontaneously jump together when brought within a distance of a few nanometres from one another and a "perfect solid" cannot be overemphasised.

In 1932 Bradley (20) reported using this concept of work of adhesion to calculate the mechanical force F needed to separate from molecular contact two spherical particles of the same substance of diameter D and found the result to be

$$F = \frac{3\pi}{8} WD \quad [2]$$

(21)

In the equation, the surface forces pulling the spheres together and tending to increase the area of contact are balanced by the elastic forces of deformation of the spheres. It is clear that what actually goes on at the edge of the surface of contact is not to be described macroscopically but is a property of the material itself. The same problem of description as found in describing the tip of a crack.

Figure 2

- A. Two spheres in contact with a force F applied to separate them
 B. Peeling of an elastic film from a rigid surface
 C. Cracking of a lap joint
 After Kendall - reference 24

The same methodology can be applied to different geometrics Rivlin (22) peeled a polymer film from a rigid substrate and showed that the same equation applies without the factor $\frac{3\Pi}{8}$ by replacing D - the sphere diameter by the film width b , cf also (23) who show that the same equation is followed independently of the elastic properties of the peeling material in this test; and also show that the equation also applies to the trouser leg tear test provided the tearing strip (trouser legs) remain(s) vertical since potential energy is converted directly to overcome the work of adhesion. When the materials of the joint are stretched significantly as in Fig 2C the elastic modulus E of the materials(s) and the thickness d are involved and the equation becomes

$$F = b(4WE d)^{1/2} \quad [3]$$

which bears a remarkable resemblance to the Griffith equation.

These equations show that the (measured) adhesive force can vary substantially with the geometry of the test and with the stiffness of the material tested, as well as with the quantity W which is a measure of the surface forces. I have introduced equation 2 in order to use it to show why physical adhesion is not normally considered in engineering situations but dominates at a scale of size of some nanometres.

Kendall (24) points out that a ball bearing of 10 mm diameter with a dirty (normal?) surface with a value of $W = 0.1\text{Jm}^{-2}$ (~ 100 ergs/cm²) - most measured surface energies of polymers are about 0.1Jm^{-2} and of metals and ceramics are between 0.5 and a few Jm^{-2} - would experience an adhesive force of about one millinewton. The force of terrestrial gravity on such a ball bearing is about 40 Newtons. So the force of adhesion is negligible in comparison.

Figure 3
 Comparison of the force of adhesion with the force of gravity for
 smooth and rough spheres of varying diameter
 After Kendall - reference 24

(from Kendall) compares the force of adhesion for very smooth and very rough spheres with the force of gravity. It is seen that at a sphere diameter about 1000 nm i.e. $1\mu\text{m}$ the force of gravity greatly exceeds the adhesive force. For very smooth surfaces, really well prepared, the transition takes place at a sphere diameter of about 1 mm.

The diameter of the fibres used in composites varies between a few microns and say 25 μm . From the above consideration I think it is clear why one of our difficulties of understanding the mechanics of the interface between fibre and matrix arises. The surface forces of adhesion which act irresistibly strongly over small distances are of course greatly modified by surface layers of fluid - the adhesion of mica is reduced by a factor of five in water. Experiments on some rubbers show that wetting and non wetting liquids measured by the contact angle θ change the molecular adhesion in opposite senses - non wetting increasing adhesion and wetting liquids reducing it.

$\theta = 0$ wets on a smooth surface, spontaneously $\theta > 0$ does not wet; but then surface roughness affects spreading and so long as $\theta < 90^\circ$ a liquid may spread by capillary action along scratches and fine pores. Surface roughness is important. If $\theta < 90^\circ$ roughening a smooth surface decreases the apparent θ ; if $\theta > 90^\circ$, roughening increases the apparent θ . It is generally found that fluids which spread on a solid surface reduce molecular adhesion because the surfaces cannot jump together but are separated by a layer of "molecular" contamination. That fact runs counter to experience with engineering "adhesives" where wetting will generally increase adhesion by filling gaps and forming an intimate interface. The diameter of fibre with which we are concerned in composite mechanics is precisely in the range where the preponderance of the forces of molecular adhesion are being overtaken by the forces of adhesion "engineered" by adhesive technology. The principles of engineering adhesion in this sense are well covered by Kinloch (25).

The surfaces between real materials in air are never smooth, never chemically pure and are not representative of the bulk material. Any type of join such as that found in the case of

Bradleys experiments will only, if it exists at all, be present possibly at a small number of isolated sites. Sometimes the presence and strength of these can be measured and correlated with mechanical tests. The example I shall now give is of adhesive bonding of a fibre composite to another one, rather than that of fibre to matrix in a composite.

Kinloch Kodokian and Watts (26) stuck together unidirectional composites with an epoxy resin (thermosetting) matrix or with various thermoplastic matrices. The adhesive used was either a cold curing or a hot curing epoxy resin; the cold cured adhesive being much the tougher of the two. A Corona discharge treatment was necessary with the thermoplastic matrices in order to ensure that fracture occurred within the adhesive layer. Surface treatment, determination of the surface chemistry and the mechanical tests by double cantilever beam were beautifully correlated.

The locus of joint failure illustrates beautifully the difficulties we have in attacking the problem of understanding the mechanical properties of the interface and relating these to chemical and physical binding at the interface. When the bonded joint fails by interlaminar fracture of the composite substrate, the value of fracture energy is significantly lower than when the locus is through the adhesive, and it is equal to the interlaminar fracture energy of the composite material. Such an interlaminar crack propagates at an applied load below that associated with failure through the adhesive. Because the cold cured adhesive is tougher than the hot cured one there is a much greater tendency for the joints made with the cold cured resin to show interlaminar failure. The measured transverse stress generated with the cold cured resin is much greater than that generated with a hot cured one. The locus of joint failure for DCB joints is governed by the value of the transverse tensile stress generated in the composite substrate in the region of the crack, with respect to the transverse fracture stress of the composite. However, this easily understood result only follows when a sufficient surface treatment has been applied to the composite so as to prevent failure of the composite adhesive interface. The locus of failure is therefore governed by the ease of interlaminar cracking in the composite substrate, rather than the energy (and hence load) needed to (subsequently?) propagate this interlaminar crack through the composite substrate.

In order to ensure a "good bond" i.e. one of high toughness it must therefore be ensured that both the toughness of the adhesive layer be larger than that of the substrate(s) and that the stress to initiate crack propagation within the adhesive layer be lower than that to initiate (grow) a crack within the substrate(s). Provided this stress condition is fulfilled (and only if it is) then there is some point to using an adhesive which is tougher (for a crack running parallel to the interface) than the substrate material.

Only when the above mechanical conditions have been satisfied can some clear correlation be established between the chemistry of the adhesive and values of the fracture energy for a crack running within it. The correlation found in this case was firstly that a critical intensity of surface treatment to the thermoplastic matrix composite was necessary to prevent interfacial failure. This critical intensity depends upon the polar force component of the surface free energy. It was possible to find the polar force component of the surface free energy of the thermoplastic from contact angle measurements with various polar liquids, see general references to Kinloch (25). The only caveat which can be entered against the mechanical measurements in these beautiful experiments is the ignorance of the value of any residual stress, say with the hot cured adhesive. They yield a knowledge of how to ensure that the measured mechanical properties of the joint are governed by the properties of the adhesive.

When adhesives are not used correlation between some measure of the chemical activity of the surface of the fibre and a "shear strength" via pull out is sometimes possible, e.g. (27) but as the authors readily admit relatively uncertain.

Ever since carbon fibres were discovered it has been known that they did not "bond well" to epoxy resins. The known treatments up to about 1993 are listed by Jones (28) who finds that there was no correlation between amount of chemical functionality introduced into the fibre surface and the fibre/resin bond strength and believes this to be due to the fact that the immediate surface concentration of chemical groups is too low. This is because the surface treatments roughen the surface, have variable penetration, expel some

impurities, dry the fibre, etc. - the fibre surface is "the floor of a chemical laboratory" with unknown reagents spilt on it". Special methods to greatly increase the number of active groups e.g. by nitrogen plasma treatment does appear to produce a correlation (29).

In practical engineering terms we may not be able to wait for a complete understanding of the interface mechanics and chemistry and their correlation before designing some interfaces of practical utility - sizes on glass fibres to be incorporated into composites have been identified for many years - they usually protect the glass fibre from damage by water vapour and show some compatibility with the resin.

The problem is quite acute with CMCs designed for high temperature use since any interface must be stable for long periods at temperatures where atomic diffusion will occur - not too strong in a cohesive sense so that a crack can distinguish between fibre and matrix - and able to shear so as to provide toughness by pull out.

Morgan and Marshall (30) have produced some very useful rules for the design of functional interfaces in oxide/oxide composites, concentrating on sapphire which illustrates well a general difficulty. Being amphoteric it can react readily with either acidic or with basic oxides, which must hence be avoided. Lanthanum phosphate the basis of the mineral monazite was found to be a useful suggestion because of its softness.

The question of stability at high temperature raises the question of whether the matrix and fibre should be of the same composition so as to prevent interdiffusion. A surface coating may be necessary on the fibres to fabricate the composite; thereafter it could be sublimed or burned off - the fugitive interface. A material of the same composition as fibre (and matrix) but with lower modulus (i.e. more compliant) could be produced by making the interface "holey" or porous (31). The required friction between fibre and matrix might be obtained solely by undulating the interface. There are many suggestions.

It is absolutely clear that better understanding of micromechanics is necessary for the solution to the problems.

4. DENSITY OF FIBRE PACKING

Micro considerations are necessary, if not micromechanics, in order to decide on optimum arrangements of individual fibres and bundles of fibres. In pmcs fibres and fillers are often used together and optimum arrangement of the two are useful as Milewski has emphasised (32) (33) together with Evans and Gibson (34).

The random packing of long straight fibres of finite length has been investigated by Milewski and by Evans and Gibson and by Parkhouse and Kelly (35). The latter derived an empirical relationship between attainable packing density and aspect ratio (l/d) of the fibres. The limiting density is given by

$$V_f = \frac{2}{(l/d)} \ln(l/d) \quad [4]$$

a formula which is valid up to a value of $l/d \sim 3$. Milewski's results may also be used to show that equation (4) applies to the median (average) value if fibres of varying l to d ratio are used - which greatly increases the utility of the semi-empirical formula.

Experimental investigation of the packing of (approximately) spherical particles has been considered by a large number of authors. The limiting packing density found for single size sphere is very close to $\frac{5}{8}$ or 0.625. This figure is the same as that found by Parkhouse and Kelly (36) for the limiting density of packing of straight rods placed normal to the faces of a rhombic dodecahedron - the packing of rods of the highest cubic symmetry. They also found that the highest density they were able to predict for rods stacked in an aperiodic fashion; each rod directed along the normal to the faces of a regular (pentagonal) dodecahedron was about 0.15 (see below). Parkhouse and Kelly also

calculate the elastic modulus of their fibre arrays. When the packing of spheres of two different sizes was investigated the highest packing density found was close to ($\frac{1}{2}$) - 80%.

Table 1 compares the moduli attainable in a composite containing fibres, and compares this with that attainable with spheres of uniform diameter and when two populations are employed so as to obtain a p.f. of 80%. If isotropy or near isotropy is sought then for large ratios of E_f to E_m fibres are superior but if E_f/E_m is say 20 (corresponding to g.r.p.) then one does better to use spheres.

TABLE 1
ISOTROPIC ARRANGEMENTS - SPHERES, FIBRES

E_f/E_m	100			20		
V_f	1/6	5/8	4/5	1/6	5/8	4/5
ISOTROPIC						
Spheres	$E_f/84$	$E_f/38$	$E_f/21$	$E_f/17$	$E_f/8$	$E_f/5$
Fibres	$E_f/36$			$E_f/24$		
NEAR ISOTROPIC						
Max	$E_f/8$			$E_f/8$		
Min	$E_f/14$			$E_f/14$		

The practically important case of mixtures of spheres and fibres has also been investigated experimentally by Milewski.

Parkhouse and Kelly (36) have investigated repeating patterns of infinitely long straight bars to find out what is the tightest packing that can be devised for the cases of material being distributed equally in 3, 4 and 6 directions. The three directions are normal to the faces of a cube and the fibre volume fraction, V_f , is $\frac{3}{4}$. They also discovered arrangements based on the regular tetrahedron and on the rhombic dodecahedron which follow the same "rule" in that the directions of the bars are the same as the normal to the faces of their associated solids and their bar sections are the same as the faces of their associated solids. The values of V_f are $\frac{1}{2}$ and $\frac{1}{3}$ respectively. In both cases closer packing can be obtained if the cross sectional shape is changed. In the tetrahedral case a regular hexagon as cross section yields a value of V_f of as high as $\frac{3}{4}$ and in the case of a rhombic dodecahedron choice of cross section of a truncated rhombus or irregular hexagon leads to a value of V_f as high as $\frac{3}{8}$ (0.625). The results are collected in Table 2.

TABLE 2

FIBRE DIRECTIONS	FIBRE CROSS SECTION	E_{\max}	E_{\min}	VOLUME FRACTION
Cube Edge	Square	$E_f/4$	0	0.75
Tetrahedral	Equi.Triangle	$E_f/8$	0	0.5
"	Reg.Hexagon	$3E_f/16$	0	0.75
Normals to Rhombic Dodecahedron	35.3°Rhombus	$E_f/15$	$E_f/27$	0.33
"	Irregular Hex. or Trunc.Rhombus	$E_f/8$	$5E_f/72$	0.625 (5/8)
Regular Dodecahedron	Regular Pentagon	$E_f/6.V$	$E_f/6.V$?? > 0.15

The arrangement of fibres along the normals to the faces of a rhombic dodecahedron provides fibres in six directions and ensures a non-zero elastic modulus in all directions. Whether an arrangement of fibres can provide an elastically isotropic composite is an intriguing question. Fibres must be arranged in at least six directions [because of the six independent components of the stress (or strain) tensor]. A regular solid with face normals running in six directions in space each equally disposed with respect to the other is the regular dodecahedron. Christensen (37) has proved that infinitely slender fibres arranged in this way with each fibre making an angle of $\tan^{-1}2$ to the others provides an elastically isotropic arrangement, but the specification of infinite slenderness implies an elastic modulus of zero. Kelly and Parkhouse have explored arrangements of bars with pentagonal cross sections each making an angle of $\tan^{-1}2$ to every other. A small number pack tightly; the question is whether a periodic arrangement exists. An arrangement involving exact translational symmetry, as in the cases of the tetrahedral and rhombic dodecahedral packing, is not possible - as can be seen from Fig.4

Pentagonal sectioned fibres $V_f > ?$

Figure 4
Illustrating the difficulty of achieving regular packing of fibres normal to a five fold axis of symmetry.

since it would require translational symmetry normal to a five fold axis of rotational symmetry - which is not possible. However, an "almost" periodic arrangement can repeat indefinitely - what is quite meant by almost is not precise - Penrose (38); one arrangement being discovered by Ogawa and Hizume - private communication. For this particular case the volume fraction found so far by Parkhouse and Kelly yields a volume fraction of only 0.15 ($\frac{1}{6}$). There is a possibility of a much larger density of packing so whether true isotropy can be obtained with fibres with a useful volume fraction is still an unsettled question.

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